

THE WAY OF DEVELOPING THE NATIONAL AND LINGUISTIC IDENTITY OF THE KAZAKH NATION THROUGH THE APPROXIMATION OF THE ABAY LANGUAGE TO THE WORLD LANGUAGE

**Karimov Bakhtiyor Rakhmanovich,
Doctor of Science (Philosophy), Professor, Leading Researcher,
Institute of Oriental Studies, Academy of Sciences of the Republic of
Uzbekistan,
karimov.bahtiyor@yahoo.com**

The great poet and educator Abay Kunanbaev made an invaluable contribution to the formation and development of the literary Kazakh language. In the process of globalization, modernization, intensification of the formation of the world information civilization, the most important task is to preserve and develop the national and linguistic identity of nations. This task is also important for the Kazakh nation in the multilingual situation in the Republic of Kazakhstan.

After achieving independence, the Republic of Kazakhstan and the Kazakh nation are making great efforts to raise the domestic and international social status of the Kazakh language. A state program has been adopted and is being implemented to support the development of the Kazakh language as the state language of the country. Centers for teaching the Kazakh language and traditions have been created. However, there are still many difficulties and unresolved problems in this direction. In the interethnic and international communication system, the Kazakh language is not used actively enough. These functions mainly use Russian and English. Together, these factors lower the social status and image of the Kazakh language. For a breakthrough accelerated increase in the social status of the Kazakh language, original non-standard solutions are required, since standard solutions do not give the expected effect in the required time frame, despite the very large allocated funds.

The purpose of this project: To provide a scientific basis for a breakthrough innovative modernization of the domestic and international social status of the Kazakh language through the creation of a closely related Averaged Turkic language Ortaturk, which has the potential to become an international language recognized by the UN [1; 2; 3; 4; 5]. To achieve this goal, it is necessary to solve the following tasks: 1) create the Averaged Turkic language Ortaturk; 2) to create a coordinated and unified system of alphabets of the national Turkic languages

and the Ortaturk language; 3) to create a coordinated terminological system of the Turkic languages and the Ortaturk language.

The Averaged Turkic language Ortatürk in lexical aspect will be close to the language of Abai (1845-1904), one of the last classics who wrote in the literary Turkic language before the legal transformation of this great language into a dead language in 1924. This chauvinistic, denying the right of nations to self-determination action to destroy the Turkic language was carried out during the so-called "national-state delimitation" carried out through mass terror under the leadership of Stalin without revealing the free will of the people of Turkestan.

The implementation of this project of creating the Ortaturk language and improving the functioning of the Turkic languages and scripts would act as a factor in the breakthrough, innovative, modernizing social development of the states and nations that are part of the Turkic and Central Asian civilizations and, in general, the World civilization.

For the socio-economic development of Kazakhstan, the implementation of this project would be of great importance, as it would allow quickly, without very large expenditures of its own resources, by the collective efforts of all Turkic-speaking peoples and UN structures, to receive basic world information and transmit their information to the world on a closely related international, world language Ortaturk. This would raise the social status and image of the Kazakh language almost to the level of international, world languages. In turn, this would lead to an increase in his domestic social status.

The following negative consequences are possible in case of refusal of this program. A strategically important historical and geopolitical opportunity for self-preservation and successful self-development of Kazakhstan, the Kazakh nation and the Kazakh language based on cooperation and mutual assistance of kindred Turkic peoples will be missed. The Kazakh language, perhaps, will be pushed aside from the main spheres of social life by such international, world languages as Russian, English and Chinese, or will be subjected to their very strong deforming effect. As a result, the linguistic, national and state identity of the population of Kazakhstan may experience great fluctuations and become unstable in the process of globalization and the powerful influence of non-Turkic geopolitical actors. This is contrary to the national interests and national security of Kazakhstan and the Kazakh nation.

There are the following main options for solving the problem of the language of inter-Turkic inter-ethnic communication: 1) Recognition of English as the leading world language, which is known by many representatives of the Turkic

peoples as the language of inter-Turkic inter-ethnic communication; 2) Recognition of the Russian language as one of the world languages, which is known by many Turkic peoples as the language of inter-Turkic interethnic communication; 3) Recognition of one of the national Turkic languages as the language of inter-Turkic interethnic communication; 4) The revival of the language "Turki" as the language of inter-Turkic interethnic communication; 5) Creation of the Averaged Turkic language "Ortaturk" by averaging the Turkic languages, recognizing it as the language of inter-Turkic interethnic communication, the language of information of general Turkic and world significance and achieving its recognition as one of the UN languages [1; 2; 3; 4; 5]. We propose to implement this fifth option, since it does not provide privileges and does not create infringement on the rights and dignity of each of the Turkic peoples, it gives them the right to use their Turkic language as the state language in their national state and develop it to the best of their ability, ensuring equality of all Turkic languages among themselves.

In the international status, the Ortaturk language would contribute to cooperation between the Turkic peoples, information and communication, spiritual and intellectual development of individuals and social groups in Kazakhstan, the Turkic world and the entire World civilization.

The processes of language development, especially the problems of changing linguistic identity, should be assessed from the point of view of the relationship between human rights and the rights of nations and linguistic groups of individuals. In the individualistic concept of personality, personality is separated from the society that formed it and is regarded as an independent, a priori, self-sufficient starting point for evaluating all the processes taking place in the world. The rights of the society, the community, the collective that formed this person are not sufficiently taken into account. It is advisable to achieve greater harmonization in the relationship between the rights of the individual and the rights of society. To do this, it is necessary to take into account the social essence of a person and a nation. In this regard, it is advisable to use the oikumenic theory of the nation, the concepts of ethnosism, ethnolinguanism, averaged languages and Averaged World language [1; 2; 3; 4; 5], which as a whole constitute a linguo-geopolitical concept leading to the synthesis of the languages of the East and West, all the languages of Mankind.

In the context of the oikumenic theory of the nation, we will consider the problems of global development and ways of preserving national cultures, languages, developing the linguistic and cultural convergence of East and West.

In these matters, it is expedient to achieve an optimal combination of universal and national interests. To ensure the unity of Mankind and preserve its diversity, it is advisable to create a system of averaged languages for groups of genealogically related languages [1; 2; 3], and later on the creation of the averaged World language through averaging in a variety of averaged languages and isolated languages based on the Nostratic (Borea) concept, the concept of language universals and statistical methods for averaging language phenomena [1; 2; 3]. The world auxiliary language created in this way for intercultural, interethnic communication, accumulation of world information and global learning would contribute to the solution of many global problems of world civilization and the spiritual mutual enrichment of all local civilizations and peoples. The creation of the averaged world language could act as a way for the linguistic and cultural convergence of East and West within the framework of a single Humanity system with the preservation of national and civilizational identity.

These projects correspond to the trends and prospects for the development of intercultural communication in the process of formation of the world information civilization in the 21st century. They are aimed at solving the problems of multilingualism in Kazakhstan in the sphere of national-linguistic relations on the basis of the principles of equality, the sovereignty of states, ensuring human rights and freedoms and the collective rights of social groups (national, linguistic, ethnic, racial, confessional, etc.). The creation of the Averaged Turkic language Ortaturk, which in the lexical aspect will be close to the language of Abay, will lead to the revival of the Turkic languages as one of the international, world languages. This will allow the Kazakh language to act as an almost world language in relation to such world languages as Russian, Chinese and English.

Literature:

1. Каримов Б.Р., Муталов Ш.Ш. Ўртатурк тили. Тошкент: Мехнат, 1992.
2. Karimov B.R, Mutalov Sh. Sh. Averaged languages: an attempt to solve the world language problem. Tashkent: Fan, 1993 (второе изд. в 2008 году, третье издание в 2019 году).
3. Каримов Б.Р., Муталов Ш.Ш. Усредненные языки: попытка решения мировой языковой проблемы. Ташкент: Фан, 2008. (второе изд. в 2019 году).
4. Karimov B. The oikumenic concept of nation and problems of development of languages. Ойкуменическая концепция нации и проблемы развития языков. Qarshi, 2003.
5. Каримов Б.Р. Ойкуменическая концепция нации и проблемы

развития языков. Якутск, 2004.